

In Search of Isomorphism: An Analysis of the Homepages of Flagship Universities

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1. Introduction

Flagship universities are leading universities in different national higher education systems. With the emergence of global university rankings, they have become 'peers' in an imagined global higher education system and 'competitors' in the global knowledge economy. However, the concepts of a global higher education system and a global knowledge economy are equally vague. This suggests that such national flagship universities with a global role are facing a highly uncertain external environment in which they operate. The discourse of global competition further drives them into a state of insecurity, resulting in changes that are believed to have led to the homogenization of university models.

Based on a content analysis of the websites of 58 flagship universities in 39 different countries listed on Shanghai Jiao Tong's *Academic Ranking of World Universities* in 2009, this paper seeks to investigate whether there is a global communication model found among this supposedly homogeneous group of universities. Specifically, it will first highlight major changes observed in the homepages of the sampled flagship universities captured in April 2010 and November 2011. It will then continue with a critical analysis of the homogeneity and diversity of the homepages of the flagship universities using a mix of conceptual frameworks, mainly of isomorphism, but also strategic planning, diffusion of innovation and travel of ideas. Finally, it will conclude with a reflection on the perceived role of flagship universities in global higher education and the knowledge economy in relation to their external communication strategy (or the lack of it).

2. Rationales and Research Methods

The heterogeneity of higher education systems around the world suggests that comparing universities in different systems is a 'mission impossible'. However, there are several so-called global or world university rankings which have caught

considerable attention not only of students and parents, but also of policymakers and higher education practitioners in charge of internationalisation and research cooperation. Apart from misinformation, critics of these rankings warn against the phenomena of “isomorphism” and “academic drift” in the higher education sector resulting from the rankings’ narrow emphases on indicators limited to hard sciences, past performances, or simply reputation. There is, therefore, the fear that national higher education systems and individual institutions may forgo their original mission and uniqueness in pursuit of a ‘world-class’ status or a ‘global university model’ propagated through such popularised global university rankings. The fear is not unfounded. A number of studies, notably one by Ellen Hazelkorn (2008), have found “unintended” negative impacts of such rankings on international collaboration, research funding allocation, as well as national and institutional policies. There is, however, little research with a focus on the relationship between global university rankings and the symbolic capital of the universities. This is a gap that should be filled, especially when it becomes increasingly clear that global university rankings are more about reputation-building than about the measurement of the actual quality of higher education and research.

Rankings may not reflect the actual quality of an institution in comparison to its peers. But the ranking information itself has no doubt a symbolic indicative value, be it positive or negative, for institutional communication. In the realms of public relations and marketing, the appeals of emotion, prestige and status often override factual information. Universities that are ranked well or ranked better than their peers rarely resist against the temptation to communicate their ranks for institutional branding. With the prevailing discourse of global competition, such temptation can only grow stronger.

In the global competitive environment, universities traditionally strong in their national systems are now assigned a new mission to increase their countries’ appeal to students, talented researchers and resources which are critical to the development of the knowledge economy but are prone to be globally mobile. These universities, referred to as “flagship universities” (Altbach and Balán 2007, pp. 7-8), are not only expected to compete but also to communicate in a global environment. With their global role, they do not only have to bring their research and teaching quality to align with certain global standards, which are subject to interpretation, but also to communicate their achievements globally in order to attract the mobile talents and resources.

However, how and how well do these flagship universities communicate globally? Have they capitalised on their global ranks? If so, how do they present such information on their websites? More importantly, does this particular group of universities driven into the global ranking races display a tendency to adopt also a global communication model by resembling their peers in the selected group or emulating the top-ranked universities? In other words, are there traits of isomorphism seen in the self-representation of such flagship universities? If so, what are

the isomorphic features and what features remain different? Finally, do these differences or similarities fit the purpose of raising the global attractiveness of the universities in a competitive environment?

The above questions have led to the study of the homepages of 58 flagship universities ranked among the top 500 in the *Academic Ranking of World Universities* (ARWU, also commonly known as the “Shanghai Jiaotong” ranking) in 2009. The selected universities represent 39 different countries from both developed and developing countries. They were all ranked 1st in their respective countries. Due to tied ranks in the following countries: (see number of universities shown in parenthesis) Belgium (4), Chile (2), Hungary (2), Italy (3), New Zealand (2), Poland (2), and Portugal (2), and the fact that China was represented as three separate entities – with China (6), Hong Kong (3) and Taiwan (1) –, 58 instead of 39 universities were sampled for analysis. Their homepages, as well as webpages with ranking information that are a maximum of three clicks away from the homepages, were coded in April 2010 and November 2011 using the same coding scheme covering the following aspects: language option(s), visual style of the homepage, the use of social media that are global icons today, content of featured image, and, last but not the least, the use of ranking information.

Using the coded data, quantitative content analysis of the homepages and qualitative content analysis of the ranking information used on the homepages were conducted. Where quantitative analysis was conducted for national or regional comparisons, weighting was adjusted for countries where more than one university was represented. It must also be noted that much of the analysis in this study was based on the coded data of the English version of the universities’ websites, given that English is the only language that is used by all the universities sampled for the study.

3. Development Towards a Transdisciplinary Conceptual Framework

Although higher education research has developed into a transdisciplinary field of study in its own right, conceptual frameworks for explaining higher education developments have largely been borrowed from other disciplines such as sociology, political sciences and economics. There is not yet any established theory for higher education *per se* and none that can be readily applied in this study of an important yet currently peripheral aspect of higher education – university marketing and communication.

The author has, therefore, called on various concepts that have been developed in sociology, economics and communication to form a ‘cocktail’ conceptual framework for this study. Central to this framework is the concept of “isomorphism” which has been used frequently in studies concerning higher education institutions in a globalised environment (Stensaker and Norgard 2001; Marvin and Marc 2004; Gounko and Smale 2007; Loomis and Rodriguez 2009; Shirish,

Thompson and Annapoornima 2009), particularly, when assessing the impact of global university rankings.

During the literature review, it was, however, found that the concept of isomorphism itself is subject to clarification. To clarify the concept of isomorphism and its possible application in the context of higher education research, a conceptual framework (Figure 1) focusing on the concept of isomorphism and relevant concepts has been constructed for this study. Details of the framework are illustrated below.

Figure 1: A Cocktail Conceptual Framework Proposed by the Author for Analysing Higher Education Marketing and Communication

By applying the concept of isomorphism, the phenomenon that universities (and their websites in the case of this study) around the world begin to *look alike* should be explained in relation to the *uncertain* external environment (Appold 2005, p. 20; Birnbaum 2001, p. 181; DiMaggio and Powell 1983; Gounko and Smale 2007, p. 535; Jaeki and Fatemeh 2005, pp. 1222-1223; Shirish et al. 2009; Marvin and Marc 2004, p. 85; Simon 2005, p. 5) that gives rise to isomorphic changes. The external environments surrounding universities are constantly changing as a result of globalization and the ensuing neo-liberalist approach in public administration. Market forces have deregulated or liberalised the higher education sector, opening up the higher education 'market' for competition from

local private providers or overseas providers (Mok and Tan 2004). Even though one may argue that market forces have not penetrated all the higher education systems around the world and public universities remain in operation in some of the most marketised countries, the discourse of global competition has created an uncertain external environment that appears volatile, if not hostile, to universities. Such an uncertain context surrounding universities, which have few established success models to hold on to, is represented by the cloud, and the different university models are represented by the circles in Figure 1.

In order to survive in a globally uncertain environment in which few references can be found from within the academic sector, universities tend to look to the business world for solutions, because it is both the pioneer and advocate of globalisation (Birnbaum 2001; Hemsley-Brown and Oplatka 2006; Kantanen 2007; D'Andrea et al. 2007). For example, the concept of strategic planning has been borrowed from the business world to help enhance the competitiveness of universities. From an economic perspective, competitive advantage could be achieved by differentiating oneself from the mass or by lowering ones production costs through economies of scale. Between the two, differentiation is regarded as a more sustainable strategy than waging a price war with competitors selling similar products. Thus, the essence of strategic planning in business is to differentiate. However, this very concept does not seem to have penetrated the higher education sector. While many universities are engaging in some kind of strategic planning today and are applying relevant concepts from the business world (e.g. marketing, branding) in their operation, the results of their planning are more in the direction towards isomorphism than differentiation.

This brings us to the distinction between rational and irrational strategic planning (Shirish et al. 2009), which should also be taken into account in understanding the isomorphic changes of universities. In Figure 1, such contradictory approaches are visualized with a two-end arrow which has a rational end of *differentiating*, pointing out of the uncertain cloudy environment, and an institutionalised end of *conforming*, pointing back to the cloudy environment.

Isomorphism resulting from institutionalised strategic planning, though irrational, should not be ruled out as a topic for scientific investigation. Rather, it needs to be better described and explained as it is believed to be a prevailing phenomenon in the global higher education system and is frequently associated with studies of institutional changes and innovation without much clarification of the concept itself. The term has become familiar to higher education researchers through major studies concerning the impacts of global university rankings and globalisation of higher education (Marginson 2008; Marginson 2009; van Vught 2008). However, if one takes a closer look at current literature, only a few systematic applications of the concept of isomorphism in higher education research are found and they are mostly used for explaining the impacts of quality assurance

and regulations (Gounko and Smale 2007; Hodson et al. 2008; Stensaker et al. 2009).

The study of Gounko and Smale (2007) is one of the few to have clearly demonstrated how three types of isomorphism, namely “coercive”, “mimetic” and “normative” isomorphism, can be differentiated and used to explain why higher education institutions change in response to different external forces. This study clarifies and demonstrates how isomorphism can be applied in the context of higher education research without departing from the original concept of isomorphism proposed by DiMaggio and Powell. In another study by Stensaker et al. (2009), the concepts isomorphism, isonymism and isopraxis are borrowed from Erlingsdottir and Lindberg (2005) and used to analyse the impacts of *European Standards and Guidelines* on higher education institutions’ quality assurance reviews. At first sight, one may think that the study is another example elaborating on how the concept of DiMaggio and Powell could be applied in higher education research. At closer inspection, however, it is found that although both are termed “isomorphism”, the definition and scope of isomorphism proposed by DiMaggio and Powell (1983) and Erlingsdottir and Lindberg (2005) are very different. The latter have reduced the definition of “isomorphism” to describe only the similarity of “form” and then supplemented “isomorphism” with the other two terms “isonymism” (describing the similarity of name), and “isopraxis” (describing the similarity of practice). The former, proposing a more commonly used definition, however, imply similarities in both organisational structure and procedures and their concept is often loosely applied to explain similarities among organisations that may cover all the three aspects (isomorphism, isonymism, isopraxis) distinguished by Erlingsdottir and Lindberg. In Figure 1, both sets of concepts concerning isomorphism in broad and narrow terms are incorporated after the following consideration.

Erlingsdottir and Lindberg (2005) believe that “idea” could be separated into “form”, “practice”, and “name”. Moreover, an idea travels across time and space and is translated rather than diffused. Unlike DiMaggio and Powell, their set of concepts (isomorphism, isopraxis, and isonymism) seems to be describing the *pattern of similarities* among organisations instead of the *path of influence* causing the similarities among organisations. Both sets of concepts are applicable for explaining the similarities among organisations, but the latter focuses on describing *in what ways* the organisations are similar (isomorphism, isonymism, isopraxis) and the former focuses on describing *for what reasons* the organisations have become similar (coercive, mimetic or normative isomorphism). With such an interpretation, the two sets of concepts are complementary to each other and are not exclusive to or falsifying each other.

In Figure 1, the broad definition of isomorphism and the related three forces - coercive, mimetic and normative isomorphism - are presented as arrows exerting conforming forces into a triangle delineating the immediate external environment

for an organisation undergoing isomorphic changes. The arrows are framed by solid and dotted lines to illustrate different levels of influence exerted by coercive, normative and mimetic isomorphism (the more solid the stronger the force). The narrow definition of isomorphism (concerning only form), as well as isonymism and isopraxis, are then presented as three overlapping circles which demonstrate how organisations undergoing isomorphic changes could be similar or remain different in terms of form, name and practice.

It is important to see isomorphism from the three aspects of form, name and practice, although in reality, they likely to come as a package when universities emulate others. The reason is that even when organisations undergo radical changes in order to look like another organisation, they are bound to be different in the *degree* of similarities either due to an inability to imitate or due to conscious adjustments necessary to fit local conditions. In other words, while the ultimate goal of organisations undergoing isomorphic changes may be to reach an identical status as the brighter, higher positioned model in terms of name, form and practice, i.e. reach the position represented by the cross at the very centre of the three overlapping circles in Figure 1, it will never occur in reality. If and when this happens, it may better be described as cloning rather than isomorphism. Organisations reaching this point will completely lose their self-identity and become shadows of the source of influence, the big circle at the top right corner of the cloud in Figure 1. This is also where radical isomorphism most clearly contradicts the goal of differentiation, branding and strategic planning for surviving in a competitive environment.

In addition to isomorphism and strategic planning, the concepts “diffusion of innovation”, first introduced by Everett Rogers (1962), and “travel of ideas”, as described by Erlingsdottir and Lindberg, may be drawn to explain the similarities and differences in the universities’ use of communication tools. Again, the concepts “diffusion of innovation” and “travel of ideas” are rather different from each other despite the fact that they both seem to be tracing the sources of isomorphic changes. Commonly associated with the concept of isomorphism, the concept “diffusion of innovation” implies an unequal power relation between the source of influence and the organisation undergoing isomorphic changes. Compared with the concept “travel of ideas”, the term “diffusion” implies the flow of ideas from a high pressure to a low pressure environment and “innovation” implies that the ideas flowing to the low pressure area is newer (or perceived to be newer) than the one that will be changed or discarded. With the concept “travel of ideas,” there is however no such a sense of direction or comparative newness, which often implies also a sense of superiority. Rather, it suggests the possibility of influences on equal terms without bringing in the notion of pressure or a power relation. Nevertheless, I have included both in Figure 1 because they are complementary in explaining isomorphism between organisations in different sectors (e.g. business and higher education) or organisations in the same sector but of different ranks.

The 'cocktail' conceptual framework proposed above is a remix of concepts that have been used in sociology, business and communication research. Given that higher education is still a green field without an established theory of its own, such a contingent remix of concepts is, perhaps, a way towards the creation of a transdisciplinary theoretical ground for further research of higher education developments, and in particular, peripheral developments in marketing and communication.

4. How and how well do Flagship Universities Communicate Globally?

4.1 A General Switch from Text-Based to Image-Based Homepages

University websites are rarely studied by communication researchers or higher education researchers. They are perceived as a standard, if not simple, information sharing platform with little creativity or substance of interest to be researched. In the field of higher education, they are also of peripheral importance in the sense that they primarily interest the practitioners who are involved in student recruitment and marketing rather than higher education researchers who have more important issues (e.g. governance, funding, knowledge transfer) to deal with.

The lack of attention given to university websites by researchers of different fields does not imply that nothing interesting is happening in this area. On the contrary, fast and significant changes can be observed among the 58 institutions covered in this study. In the period April to August 2010, when the first round of coding and analysis took place, three universities, namely Oslo (Norway), Tehran (Iran), and Jagiellonian (Poland) launched completely new homepages, replacing their former text-based homepages with imaged-based homepages. Between August 2010 and November 2011, when the second round of coding and analysis was conducted, an additional two universities, namely Harvard (US) and Tsinghua (China), launched completely new homepages. A number of Chinese and Italian universities, together with Tokyo (Japan) and Istanbul (Turkey) also made face-lifting changes to their homepages, but only in one language version. The Chinese and Japanese universities had revamped their English homepages and kept the first language homepages intact, while the Italian universities and the University of Istanbul did just the opposite.

In short, notable changes, though at a different pace, have been spotted in the course of this study. However, it appears that not all the changes could be explained with the rationales of increasing global visibility or attracting (English-speaking) international students, as shown in the Italian and Turkish cases. This analysis does not rule out the possibility that they all intended to do so, but the changes may have misfired and missed their targets.

Without much surprise, it is also noted that when universities launch a new homepage, there is a tendency to change from a static text-based homepage to an

animated image-based homepage. The only one that runs against this tendency is Harvard. It changed from an image-based homepage with very little text to a text-based homepage with text boxes linked to its various social media websites. The general switch from static text-based to animated image-based homepages may be viewed as a sign of mimetic isomorphism, if the older Harvard homepage is taken as a benchmark. This is, however, an over-simplified conclusion as the force of coercive isomorphism exerted by the adoption of new information technology (IT) in the higher education sector and the force of normative isomorphism with the growing acceptance of images in higher education marketing and communication are non-negligible. Further investigation into the institutional decision-making process is needed to verify which of the isomorphic forces play a decisive role in the changes. Besides, even if there is mimetic isomorphism, as some universities' homepages do resemble the older Harvard homepage in form, the impact of isomorphism are likely to be found among the followers themselves rather than the object of emulation. What is evident here is that Harvard remains different in a snap.

4.2 A Trend in Adopting Social Media by Highly Ranked Flagship Universities

By comparing the data collected in April 2010 and November 2011, a clear trend in the adoption of social media, such as Facebook and Twitter, is observed. The numbers of flagship universities that have integrated Facebook and Twitter into their homepage have grown by 157% and 76% respectively during the study period. In absolute terms, these two social network platforms have overtaken RSS, which used to be the most popular means for universities to disseminate news from their homepages. Another new medium, the video-sharing platform YouTube, has also gained a noticeable increase of 60%, from 7.5 to 12 institutional users. While YouTube has not replaced RSS due to the different nature of information they deal with (i.e. video vs. text), it appears to have grown at the expense (or snubbed the growth) of two other means of communication that were found on the universities' homepages earlier, namely university promotional videos (for institutional profiling) and Open-source Course Ware (OCW) and Podcasts (for sharing recorded visual or audio format of the universities' lectures). This trend in the adoption of new communication tools has contributed to an isomorphic change of the universities' homepages and is largely driven by European universities which had been resisting the adoption of social media, in comparison with universities in Saudi Arabia or Israel, until recently.

The sudden surge in the use of social media in Europe may be interpreted as normative isomorphism instead of mimetic isomorphism, since many European universities had been using social media unofficially (if not reluctantly) until they integrated the logos of such media into their homepages officially. Although we cannot rule out the possibility that some universities (such as the ones in Saudi

Arabia and Israel), which are early adopters of social media, had the intention to mimic top-ranked English-speaking universities by incorporating social media icons into their homepages, the later adopters of social media are likely driven by the need to acknowledge and accept the changing communication habits of the new generation of (international) students.

Another potential form of isomorphism in force is coercive isomorphism, not in the form of regulations but standardization of IT tools and software, as it is observed that the use of images and animation on university homepages on one hand, and the use of social media on the other, appears to grow in parallel or reinforce each other. This is true in most cases, because universities that have launched a new website clearly have a tendency to incorporate also social media links to their new homepages.

It must be noted, however, that the norm to adopt big social media brands, such as Facebook, Twitter and YouTube, is far from global and that coercive isomorphism imposed by the IT world may be countered by state regulations. For example, it is widely known that Facebook, YouTube, Twitter are all banned in China, where the 'netizens' are active but using Chinese versions of social media. It is therefore not a surprise to see the unanimous absence of the banned social media on brand new websites of Chinese universities. This can clearly be understood as coercive isomorphism among Chinese universities as a result of regulatory constraints.

Another interesting observation is the comparatively slower pace (though there are also signs of increase) of Asian universities (e.g. Hong Kong, South Korea, New Zealand and Singapore) in adopting social media as official communication channels when compared to their quick adoption of imaged-based web design. There are likely many reasons behind these universities' hesitance in embracing social media, but one of the reasons is probably their heavy reliance on Chinese students as the source of foreign students. For this reason, there is clearly little need for developing a means of attraction that cannot get the message across to the target students.

Despite a slower than expected trend in the adoption of social media among Asian universities, flagship universities, in general, appear to have become more 'communicative' via their homepage by integrating different types of new media for either one-way information dissemination or interactive communication, or both, during the period of this study. The major difference observed among them is a general pattern that lowest ranked universities have a tendency to use one-way closed communication means (e.g. virtual tours, promotion video) more than highly ranked universities, which are, by contrast, more open to the use of interactive social media. Such a difference in the openness to communicate may be a result of the differences in the culture of communication, as well as the confidence to maintain a positive image in an open and interactive environment. The lack of expertise and resources for the maintenance of social media communication is another po-

tential explanation. Further studies are required, however, to explain the different means of communication adopted by universities as the data collected in this study focus only on their representation.

4.3 A General Increase in the Use of English, while Multilingualism is Promised

4.3.1 *Multilingualism Prevails on the Homepages of Flagship Universities*

While English is commonly regarded as the *lingua franca* in the global academic community, the role of English in the virtual representation of the flagship universities is not as strong as one may have assumed. After adjusting the weighting of the tie-ranked universities, only 8.3 of the flagship universities in the 39 countries use English as the first language of their websites. English is only one of the 26 languages used among this group of universities, meaning that language diversity still prevails in the academia, virtually. English is, however, the most widely represented language in the 39 countries since some former British colonies have kept using English as their first academic language while providing selected webpages in their first languages. Similarly, it is noted that Spanish and Portuguese have also been adopted as the first language of the websites of South American universities, but the global impact of these two languages is much smaller compared to English.

Little change in the choice of first language has been witnessed in the period April 2010 to November 2011. But some universities have been found to have strengthened their web-presentation in their second or third languages. All the flagship universities have also been found to have had a separate English (or what they labelled as the “international”) version of their websites by November 2011. A visible increase in the offer of Chinese language as a language option on Italian and some Eastern European universities’ websites has been observed.

It is not uncommon to find universities offering more than one additional language to include other widely spoken languages such as Chinese, Spanish, French and German, as well as languages of the natives (e.g. Afrikaans, Xhosa, Māori) and of their close neighbours (e.g. Korean in the case of the *University of Tokyo*, Swedish in the case of the *University of Helsinki*). The prevalence of multilingualism is far from global, however, as universities in English-speaking countries (i.e. the United States, the United Kingdom, Canada, Australia, and Ireland) only offer one language option – English. Besides, a close examination of the bilingual and multilingual websites, typically found in European and South American universities, reveals that the bilingual or multilingual approach is sometimes symbolic and most of the time limited in scope. One clear example is *Pierre and Marie Curie University – Paris 6* which ambitiously displays four language options, but two of them (Chinese and Spanish) had been completely non-functional during the period of this study.

4.3.2 *English Strengthens its Foothold as the Second Language of University Websites*

Multilingual websites are clearly high maintenance. One may then assume that flagship universities offering only two languages, their local language and the most common second language (English) would perform better in delivering their promised options. Such an assumption may be supported by the dominant belief that English is an established *lingua academia*, particularly among flagship universities which have a global mission. This is however not supported by the findings in this study. The breadth, depth and overall quality of the English websites of the flagship universities vary to a great extent. The most limited use of English was found in *University Libre Bruxelles (ULB, Belgium)* back in April 2010, when it provided only one single English webpage hidden under a French menu bar on its front page. Seemingly better, some universities offer identical websites with their first language and English. With this approach, they may have used the same template of homepage, but the richness of the content is far from identical. In the worst case, from a communication perspective, the English homepages are translated from the original version, but only partially and unsystematically on the same page, thus projecting a ‘messy-lingual’ rather than multilingual impression. One such example is the *University of Lisbon’s* homepage at the time of this study.

Despite the chaos described above, the 58 universities sampled are found to have substantially increased the use of English both in breadth and depth. The most drastic changes in the English homepages are observed in mainland China (except Hong Kong and Taiwan), Chile, Argentina, Hungary, Poland, Italy, and Japan. One common characteristic found among them is a loose link between the English websites and first-language websites. This may be explained by a clear differentiation of target users, i.e. home students vs. foreign students (for admission into English-taught programmes), as shown in the case of the *University of Tokyo*, and thus clearly differentiated English websites free from the constraints of the original. The loose link may also be an indicator of work in progress as illustrated in the case of the *University of Tsinghua* (China), which had first introduced an English website, and only later, a Chinese one of the same design in 2011.

Slowly, a wider use of English is also found in Europe. The ULB had substantially enriched its English webpages and put an eye-catching “English” icon on the homepage by November 2011. Many more European universities have increased the amount of English information on their websites, while refraining from labeling English as English. They termed their English websites as “international”. This seemingly politically neutral term has, however, ironically acknowledged English as the “international language”, especially when the “international” label is coupled with the image of a Union Jack, as shown on the website of the *University of Milan*.

Using the conceptual framework of isomorphism, if the use of English on the international websites of universities today is interpreted as normative isopraxis at a global level, national regulations and deep-rooted traditions on the use of the first language as opposed to foreign languages can be interpreted as coercive isopraxis at the national or regional level countering the influence of English. As a result of the counterforces, the normative isopraxis in the use of English has in fact resulted in, to some extent, mimetic isonymism in the promise of more English (or multiple other languages) that remains, however, iconic with less than expected substance and effect in global communication.

In light of the above analysis, the language options made available by the flagship universities on their websites should be studied alongside both their global aspirations to recruit internationally and the political influence on their choices of languages. The reason is that flagship universities are largely publicly-funded. As a result of that, they are not only more likely to be regulated (linguistically) but are also more likely to be bound by traditions and localized expectations given their national standing. Such socio-cultural and political contexts unique to flagship universities' existence must not be overlooked when explaining the seemingly schizophrenic approaches in which these universities present and position themselves.

5. Have Flagship Universities all Capitalised on Their Global Ranks Symbolically?

5.1 An Overview of the Use of Ranking Information

All the universities sampled in this study were ranked among the world's top 500 universities and the topmost university of their respective countries by ARWU. In theory, they are the ones who can reap the benefit of the ranking results for brand-building, at least at a national level. But, in practice, how many of them are using the ranking results on their homepage? The answer is: very few, if we only look at the homepage (i.e. the front page) of the university websites. In each of the coding exercise conducted in 2010 and 2011, only two universities were found to have made explicit reference to their ARWU position on the homepage. Slightly more universities (3-4) used the THES results, but this number is also very low. The only university that has been using ranking results extensively and consistently throughout the period of this study is *King Saud University* in Saudi Arabia. It was joined later by the *University of Science and Technology of China* which, since launching a new website, also displays an eye-catching banner on the homepage about its ranking positions.

The absence of ranking information on the homepage of other universities does not imply that there is no impact, however. The difference lies in the level of subtlety. Several universities have displayed the term "ranking" or ranking-related

terms such as “leading” or “top university” on their homepages, hyperlinked to detailed descriptions of their ranking results or “achievements”. This is a less eye-catching approach than displaying a banner. Yet, there is an obvious enough path directing the viewers of the homepage to the ranking results. Such an approach is commonly found among universities in New Zealand, the Nordic countries and increasingly in Eastern European countries. Moving up the level of subtlety, some universities do not display ranking information up front, but as part of the “facts and figures” or the general introduction about the university that are one to three layers below their homepages. In some cases, a ranking section or Nobel Prize winners section is displayed in parallel with the general information provided about the university without mentioning rankings on the homepage.

By taking into account more subtle expressions of the rankings such as the ones described above, over half of the universities (some 62%) in this group of 58, regardless of geographical regions and ranking positions, are using ranking information on their websites. This does not take into account sporadic ranking information given out as “news” when the annual ranking results are released, meaning that the use of ranking data by universities is bound to be more than what is presented in this study.

5.2 An Analysis of the Styles in which Ranking Information is Presented

As for *how* and *to what extent* flagship universities use ranking information on their websites, an analysis of the data collected from the 36 universities that have used ranking information shows a very diverse picture as described below.

5.2.1 Pompous Presentation Style

As mentioned earlier, only two universities carried a banner on their homepage boasting their ranking positions. Such a ‘hard-sell’ strategy is rarely found among the flagship universities analysed here. Instead, it is more common to see ranking-related messages (explicit or subtle) displayed upfront on the homepage to direct the users’ attention to more detailed messages that the universities intend to convey as “facts” or “analysis”. Compared to other more subtle expressions of rankings, we may call explicit presentation of rankings or links to rankings up front on a homepage ‘pompous presentation’, which resembles an advertisement. Eight universities were found to have used this strategy, and six among them have slogans claiming themselves as the best, the leading, the top or top-ranked university in their country or region, if not globally (depending on how the ranking positions are interpreted, creatively).

5.2.2 Analytical Presentation Style

Among the universities which do not display ranking related images or messages on the front page, eight of them dedicate a separate section or webpage to rankings, indicating that they do not take rankings lightly. Apart from the *University of Cambridge*, which is simply listing all its top ranking positions in the one-paragraph “League tables” section, the others with a dedicated section on rankings have gone to great lengths to describe their positions in different rankings and/or provided an “analysis” of their ranking positions, comparing their own ranking performance over the years or with other universities. It is interesting to note in this group that there is a tendency among European universities to first question the rankings before they bring in the analysis of their ranking positions. It is also noted that European universities, judging from where they locate the ranking information, tend to relate rankings to research, even though not all rankings they present in fact measure research outputs. By contrast, universities in the Asia-Pacific and Canada tend to link rankings to student recruitment or to their global positioning in general.

5.2.3 Factual Presentation Style

In stark contrast with the previous group, four universities mention rankings in passing in the introductory message about their university and seven simply incorporate rankings as statistics under “facts and figures” without discussion. These are less detailed presentations of rankings, but the brevity should not be taken as a sign of unimportance. On the contrary, the endorsement of the rankings and the unquestioned incorporation of the ranking figures as part of the institutional identity or statistics may indicate that rankings have been internalised in the university’s operation. In the two specific cases – the *University of Dublin* and *Utrecht University*, ranking figures were placed in a prominent position, even before the founding year of the university itself.

5.2.4 Indicative Presentation Style

However critical a university may appear in the use of ranking information and regardless of the length of the message about rankings, universities using ranking information have inherently endorsed rankings as a means for them to shape their institutional profile. Therefore, the very act of incorporating ranking information on the university website and the critical analysis displayed are contradictory in nature. One may say that while this is not ideal, it is inevitable because “rankings are here to stay”. How about Harvard, the top-most university on the ARWU ranking and many others? There is no direct reference to rankings on the website of Harvard, but the “fact” that “44 current and former faculty members” are/were Nobel Laureates is stated in the overview “Harvard at a Glance”. Such an indica-

tive presentation, avoiding the controversy of rankings while using one of the most discussed indicators that has its own established reputation, is also found in a few other old universities such as *Karolinska Institute* (est. 1810), *Moscow State University* (est. 1755) and *University of Vienna* (est. 1365). It is, however, not clear whether these universities intentionally avoid the use of rankings or if there is a lack of communication strategy. The doubt here is raised due to the following observations: *Moscow State University*, despite its high ranking position, features one of the oldest websites among the sampled universities. The “online tour” it offers from its homepage is actually a slideshow of photos. The *University of Vienna* has provided a direct link to its online university shop on the English homepage, which is not found in the most commercialized higher education systems, not to mention Europe where commercialisation of higher education remains a taboo.

5.3 A Brief Comparison in the Use of Rankings by European and Asian Universities

The analysis above suggests that the most crucial element for determining the impact of rankings is not the presentation style. Universities that display a pompous banner boasting their ranking positions are not necessarily less critical than those listing ranking information before their year of foundation as “facts and figures”. Universities that have gone into great length to explain the flaws of rankings but continue to use (or endorse) the information in order to validate their own (research) achievements may have been impacted more by rankings than those which used ranking information solely for packaging themselves and student recruitment. In the worst case, when universities use ranking data to consolidate their own position at the expense of other universities in the same system, as found in some Flemish, French and New Zealand universities, the impact of rankings on the internal balance between competition and cooperation among universities in the same national system is not negligible.

An ironic observation from this study is that European universities, which have criticised rankings the most, are using ranking information on their homepages more than Asian universities, which are believed to be obsessed with rankings. Two possible reasons may explain this discrepancy between common beliefs and the practices found in this study. First, many of the Asian universities are ranked below the top 100-200. They may not have considered the ranking positions worth mentioning. Second, rankings are more likely to affect universities that aim at attracting Asian students rather than institutions located in Asia. This is shown in the differentiated approach taken by the *Catholic University of Leuven* (Belgium) and the *University of Milan* (Italy) in adapting their Chinese and English international student recruitment brochures by including ranking information.

The above reasoning does not mean that Asian universities are not using ranking information. Rather, the decision to use ranking information or not depends also on the orientation of different Asian countries. Universities in New Zealand, as well as those in Singapore, South Korea and Hong Kong are increasingly interested in tapping into the massive outflow of students from within Asia. These universities have also begun to use ranking information to position themselves in the global higher education system by proving themselves of equal standing as, at least some of, their European or American counterparts. Such an orientation on student recruitment may also explain the use of ranking information for marketing rather than indicating research performance in Asia.

6. Discussion

As the results from this study show, the concept of isomorphism is more complex than is commonly understood. We can search for isomorphism by looking at *how* things look alike (such as similarities in forms as a result of isomorphism in a narrow sense, similarities in names as a result of isonymism, or similarities in practices as a result of isopraxism) and *why* they look alike (such as being the result of coercive, mimetic, or normative isomorphism). The kind of mimetic isomorphism that is often associated with the unintended impacts of rankings is only one out of the many sub-types of isomorphism just mentioned.

Based on the data collected in this study, universities can be similar to or different from each other as a result of various forces of isomorphism that can be reinforcing each other or restraining each other. Therefore, while there is a belief that flagship universities present in global rankings may be compelled to look like their peers on the rankings or emulate the top-ranked universities, it must be noted that the mimetic isomorphism in question can be restrained by coercive and/or normative isomorphism arising from state regulations, local norms, or the nature of universities (i.e. private vs. public).

As a result of such contending forces, it is highly unlikely to find a global model of university or a global communication model at any given time, however strong the impacts of rankings may be. It is found in this study that the flagship universities, although they are sharing increasingly similar missions to lead in the imagined global higher education system and compete in the knowledge economy, are far from homogeneous in outlook, not to mention other aspects of their operation.

This is not to say that they are all uniquely different and that there is no sign of isomorphism, however. First, there are indeed signs of mimetic isomorphism between the new image-dominant homepages adopted by some lowest ranked flagships and the older homepage of the top-ranked Harvard before it switched to a new style. However, the similarities are limited to the adoption of similar homepage templates and iconic labels rather than the content of the messages being

communicated. In other words, local adaptations are found even in cases of mimetic isomorphism.

Second, although mimetic isomorphism is found to be less prominent between universities in established national systems and the top-ranked universities, normative isomorphism is clearly reflected in the homogeneity among universities in the same world region. Such regional homogeneity, plus some noticeable signs of failed attempts to communicate through their homepages, implies that their differentiation from the top-ranked universities cannot be attributed to rational strategic planning. There is clearly conformity as a result of normative isomorphism, even though it is not at a global level nor driven by rankings.

In a positive sense, strong regional norms can help universities counter the fear of uncertainty in the changing global environment and maintain their regional diversity. In a negative sense, the counter-force of normative isomorphism may have only delayed a paradigm shift, as in the case of IT revolution and de-regularization of universities, that would ultimately have its impact at a later stage. Such diversity maintained as a result of resistance, rather than conscious differentiation, is therefore only temporary. It may disappear as time goes by.

Third, compared to normative isomorphism, coercive isomorphism appears to have a smaller role to play in the homogenization of university homepages. There are rarely hard and fast rules imposed by the states on how university websites should be designed. Though seemingly unlikely, overarching national regulations can still affect what should and should not appear on a university's homepage, even though these regulations are not applied solely to universities. At a global level, the changes in IT infrastructures and software may also result in coercive isomorphism if and when certain platforms or standards are no longer supported by existing technologies.

All in all, the findings in this study show that flagship universities in the global higher education system, if it does exist, remains virtually heterogeneous rather than homogeneous. There is a tendency to move towards homogeneity with the adoption of image-based animated homepages and the use of English and social media. But due to the different speed in the adoption of innovation and the local adaptations of imported ideas, homogeneity is highly unlikely to be found at a global scale at any given time. In other words, there is no fear of global homogeneity among the homepages of flagship universities yet, and as a result, no such thing as a 'global communication model' for flagship universities.

7. Policy Implications

In the discourse of global competition, few seem to have doubted the existence and the boundaries of a global higher education system and a global knowledge economy. While leading universities in different national systems are assigned a new mission to compete globally, there is little questioning of their suitability and

fitness for such global competition. It seems to be a natural assumption that being the top universities in their national systems, they are the best equipped to compete globally. This study challenges, to some extent, such an assumption from an institutional communication point of view. Many of these flagship universities, which are mostly publicly funded as well as heavily regulated, do not seem to be better prepared to communicate or compete globally than their private counterparts.

It is difficult to draw a line between top private universities such as Harvard and public universities by funding sources these days. But in terms of the flexibility to use the funding, the incentive to innovate, the need to take risk and to appear attractive to students, researchers and funders – in general, the adoption of a business approach in the operation –, the public-private divide is still clearly visible in most national systems. Some flagship universities have begun to privatize part of their functions in the name of university-industry partnerships, university-community engagement activities or internationalization of teaching, and to adopt a market-oriented approach in promotion. Nevertheless, they are far from being unchained from national regulations, localized socio-cultural norms, and public expectations to serve the local needs.

If the global higher education system in which they are competing is narrowly defined as racing up the global rankings, and if the global knowledge economy that they have to lead is narrowly defined as the export of higher education services, perhaps, these publicly-funded flagships are not in the best position to lead.

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